

Why are we rich or poor?

An Information scientific Point of View in our Digital Age.

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... together with Universities and Researchers worldwide ...

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Only writing down this fundamental topic may qualify the questioning person and influence the treating:

Why are we poor or rich?

... in other way ...

Why are we poor or rich?

... for my daughters Clara and Isabelle.

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1. Abstract

It's difficult to answer this question. Is it philosophical, is it economical, sociological, even ethical or religious? This topic is a really actual challenge in our Information Society.

Information Science tries to give an answer exactly to this question. Our world of work and life has to manage actually a too great amount of Information and Data. This scientific branch has the goal to come over this great challenge in a humanlike, scientific manner.

Science should not only bring detailed special knowledge – like Old Greek Sophists – it should bring precious, mental, philosophical orientations.

The generation of Scientists, who has been growing up with the Computer and realised the broad influences of modern IT (Information Technology) to our whole society is now, about 70 years after finding first Computers, obliged to reorganise some terms in our society. We recognise that our children and grandchildren have no more experience of a life without a Computer. We called them - new - the Digital Generation.

Information Science was created parallel to Informatics about 1968, as an own branch of research, interested in all what was changed by the Computer. The fascination of the technically new facts has given her leading role to general new challenges and followings for our whole society.

These Scientists seek necessary results, because they worked responsibly in leading positions in Computer Science since their starting. Our society needs trust in future happenings. It can come worse – but it shouldn't do so.

This article tries to keep economic happenings in Authors eye. Economy, Ecology and World of Work are in focus. Geo-political findings will be involved. Great, orienting guidelines will be researched and written down. Personal, human borders by being only one researcher can't be negotiated – of course.

2. Keywords

Information as term, Digital Age, Information Society, Economy, Ecology, Sustainability, Raw Materials, Food, Industry, Energies, Global Errors and Corrections

3. Fundamental Start Points

- ***The topic of this article is combined evolutionarily with the kernel of Human Being:***

- ✚ genetically,
- ✚ ontologically,
- ✚ sociologically,
- ✚ ethically.

- ***There are differences between Rich or Poor in single, human communities:***

- ✚ commercially,
- ✚ technologically,
- ✚ educationally,
- ✚ culturally.

- ***Regional, geographic differences on whole globe:***

- ✚ Industrial Countries Europe, USA, Canada, Japan,
- ✚ Russia, Industrial and Threshold Country,
- ✚ China, genuine no longer Threshold Country,
- ✚ India, Threshold Country,
- ✚ Orient, Threshold and Development Countries,
- ✚ Southern Amerika, Threshold and Development Countries,
- ✚ African Variety, Development Countries.

- ***How are the leading Industrial Countries involved?***

- ✚ historically,
- ✚ actual economically (Raw Materials, Agriculture, Industry, Energy, Ecology),
- ✚ influence of different global growth of populations.

✚ Do we need a global obliging world organisation and how can we do existing ones better in near future?

- ***What answers Information Science can give?***

✚ Philosophically,
✚ ecologically, economically,
✚ global politically and organisationally.

As you can notice this topical rough overview of questions is structured. An Information scientific entry makes sense. We can refine this doubtless, individual collection of great and highly actual questions.

Already now it's shown that the sources of differences between Poor and Rich or Rich and Poor can't be deleted. They are based in Human kernel and in the organism of Human species.

Now we can formulate the topic question more real:

Are we able - in our Digital Age – to diminish or even balance the differences between Rich and Poor in latest scientific manner? What brings Information Science for it realistically and attractively?

4. Great, general answers

- The differences between Poor and Rich isn't liftable – we can only diminish and **balance** it in a Human way.
- Human Beings, as biological beings, have **manifold biological, genetical** and various **inborn mental abilities**.
- Manifold **inborn relations by individual families, the childhood** of all of them – very especially the early one – are deciding and important in their **whole life**.
- **Ethical and material values of each family** are taken over by every child without reflection. An own, critical thinking about it is possible only at the beginning of the grown-up age – till then ontologically a lot is already learned.
- The **learned conscious knowledge** of every single person is levelled in graduations and is individually different. **Education** is a treasure for

every individual person in her whole life.

- Clear, **different social levels** are linked with **different structures of ownership** and get facts in every individuum too.
- The change of **single persons from one inborn social structure level to a „higher“ one** demands a **tremendous personally, deliberately dedication and is a show of strength for whole life.**
- **Great social and political communities** (professional associations, village, town, political party, land, state) influence the economic evaluation of every individuum.
- If social structures are **changed by violence** then in every case Human and materialistic victims are immense (f. i. World Wars in 20th century and actual regional fighting's with weapon-forces in our century).
- Generally, **great overthrow's** of these existing, socio-economic structures **by Human communities** are very **slow**, sometimes in time frames of whole Human generations.
- These **political, peaceful overthrows of** social structures got success in modern times. There are self-established republics and unified communities of them, f. i. EU.
- On the other side we realised **ecologic errors**. They aroused by the too narrow way of thinking in new technological knowledge (f. i. Pesticide, Plastic Waste). Over thrilled, genuine commercially founded applications of new findings have affected our Humanity by greed or lucre. Science has to learn to integrate the sustainability of every new product after the new product itself.
- **Evolution isn't rebuildable in some years** – we have to learn its complexity and use in greater intervals and have to respect it carefully.
- A first, welcomed, global, system analytical entry was made in 1972 by MIT. **Prof. Jay W. FORRESTER** has designed a „World Modell“ based on „System Dynamics“. Read at **Dennis MEADOWS, The Limits of Growth**, in Reference List.

5. More Details

- + **Balancing** of social differences between Poor and Rich is a successful way,
 - + because of biological and mental **abilities** of Human are real,
 - + **consideration about social structures by birth have to be respected.**
- + It's a fact that **many single persons** leave their inborn social level,
- + broad social **communities** have a motivating and orientating influence to single persons.
- + **Changes** of social structures **by raw forces of political or even weapons** have to be refused, even fought!
- + It's not yet clear how real violent measures can be fought. We have to create worldwide valid and obliged organisations; existing ones are not yet valid enough (f. i. UNO).
- + **Ecology** is based on nature which follows **evolution.**
- + The **peaceful and coordinated changes** in modern, social and political organisations is possible and is a high goal and challenge of our Digital Age.

4.1. Balance between Poor and Rich

This topic is a real first result of our Information scientific entry:

We know clearly that a full deletion of the differences between Poor and Rich are not possible, because they are not according to Human kernel.

Therefore, we set **the goal of a social balance between different human levels** (single and in groups). That can we do really!

Every try to do this by **using of force violates** some involved Human and is missing the permanent goal.

What balance can we reach?

We have to use **energy and creative power of Human Being** and let them act positively. **Humans in social pressure want – and even have to – find a binding solution.** Such a difficult and touchy, existential, social challenge can't be ordered by one single Human Being – like an instruction for work or production. The involved, social groups have to be encouraged only - to bring their needs into words and understandable presentation.

An over headed, however created Human organisation can take care on truth and legality of all involved persons only. The resulting content of this **social dialog** can and has to be fixed by all really involved groups. An over headed organisation (f. i. a state) is not allowed to influence the content of this dialog. It is allowed to take care in forms and humanlike organisation only.

The result is the balance which brings satisfaction of all involved single and grouped persons.

Not growth, but satisfaction is the new great goal in our Digital Age.

The talk or the conference has to be as long as all involved persons agree to the result.

In future social differences still will be; but all involved persons can live with them. They are all individually different but satisfied. **The best result of such a self-made balance is then a unified decision. Every not agreeing person is a diminution of the quality of a balance.**

This social balance is an indispensable goal of our Digital Age. It has to be assimilated permanently and time by time renewed. That can be organised by rules and laws. The content has to be found by involved persons only, otherwise it loses real perdurability. These organisations are allowed to introduce that dialogs only.

4.2. Conscious changes of real, predefined, social-economic structures

- Entry of **singular persons** in inborn circumstances
 - Possibilities of **changes in communities**

4.2.1. Impulse for change comes from one single person

According to personal abilities (distinct intelligence or biological talent) of a single person a need arises to leave the **inborn, social structure level** and change it into a higher one.

Sometimes even new individual properties arise.

One example is f. i. the Human type **Entrepreneur**. In surroundings at work of the author this type has been described many times as typically:

- ✚ „criminal“ or expressed creative energy,
- ✚ Individual interval in life (at about 13 till 16), with mostly hard existential circumstances,
- ✚ this “founder = prime father of an entrepreneurship“ realises his individual abilities and chances for first time in his life,
- ✚ his succeeding at his work forms him permanently and sustainably,
- ✚ if he remembers in later life, he always talks about this time period.

These lineaments are so typical and appropriate for every (new and successful) entrepreneur that they can be used as deciding criteria's for being born for an entrepreneur. You can find examples in every new enterprise.

Important is the strong will of these leading persons.

Positive for every social upgrade is the individual **intelligence**. She is inherited in about 60% biologically, genetically. Exactly then, when a single person realised, that he is more intelligent than his siblings or friends he is motivated very strong to climb into a higher social level.

If a single person realises that he is born in rich circumstances he has to show his qualities as business leader in any way. Wise fathers of such children let their sons or daughters go the same ways as they did for themselves. So, they learn all difficulties in best and fastest manner. Otherwise, “effete” children out of rich houses don't have the necessary impulse, incentive or ambition to lead an enterprise and keep it successful and sustainably

Humans can realise between themselves similar, existential and economic interests. They then build

4.2.2. social-economic and political Communities of Interests.

An important group is that one with **traditional ownership**. They have traditional and established rights and lordship. Very deciding for the success of an enterprise is the spread of interests internal of such a family of entrepreneurs.

At least in 21th century, after crash down of Communistic and State Ownerships in f. i. UDSSR or China, humanity realises that the need and ability for ownership is proper to Human kernel. Personal Human ownership is combined with responsibility for their enterprise and whole Human society (see in references in German Prof. Alfred KLOSE, 1988).

For a long-termed success of such an entrepreneur family is deciding that all members can coordinate themselves with all parts of their enterprise. No one is allowed to exploit their employed people.

Peacefully, correct and free built circumstances of ownership and control are most stable and sustainable. All concatenated individuals are then satisfied with their reached goals for themselves and for their relatives.

It's a difficult job and it has to be renewed permanently. The leadership in a commercial company needs very much sensibility and assuredness – even for long-termed interests.

The broadest danger comes then from own Human custom and not at least from too high set Human goals. Even successful figures of entrepreneurs can neglect their social surroundings and can so - by their egoism - enter the end of their enterprise. The ideal relation of all members from highest to deepest level of an enterprise is the trust in common abilities – this is very hard to reach.

4.2.3. Communities without enough possess for own life are existentially dependent.

They are enforced to get into a **trade of values** with the rich group of owners. They offer their **work, skills and knowledge** against money in form of **salary**.

In antique, simple social structures a **genuine exchange of goods in various forms (markets)** arose. Between groups of farmers on land and genuine traders in new towns first Trading Associations arose (about 10 000 b. Chr. by Phoenicians).

A group of Human without enough, inborn property for a satisfying life is even today the **second great commercial community of employed persons**. Today most of people belong to it. They built their communities of Trade Unions.

This **splitting-up Entrepreneurs or Employers – employed or working persons** is – seen globally – different from continent to continent and inside of every one.

Now, here it's not the goal of the author to make deep economic science. He doesn't have enough knowledge about it. But generally, these main headlines, terms and structures out of Information Science make sense. Our Digital Age needs it for general orientation.

4.3. What's new in our Digital Society?

- Machines, electronic equipment's and steering's are added by **Computers**.

4.3.1. What main role has the Computer for our actual economy?

- ✚ A Computer is a steering-centre by using **Software**. This **IT-system** works – once programmed – **permanently and can be repeated as often as needed**.
- ✚ Software can – separated from Computer-Hardware = Electronic – steer the Computers **by predefined and syntactically ruled text-sequences (“Programs”)**. These are constructed exclusively by Human Being as needed in every application.
- ✚ **Hardware** as well as **Software** can be **maintained (changed)** by Human Being. That is - after creating - the second main work of IT-specialists, the new good paid profession in Digital Age.

- ✚ The developed set of rules is called the **Algorithm** and is a logical

base of every IT-system.

- ✚ This, once created Computer system (IT-System) „runs“ in a wanted, complex and stored form again and again.
- ✚ It can in necessary variations be changed easily by experienced persons.
- ✚ All together is called „**Artificial Intelligence**“ (sum of all stored, artificial, automatic steering's).

4.3.2. What for is Human Being necessary?

General, abstracted and unified defined:

- to create new Hardware and Software of an IT-System,
- to plan and create chains of automatic production of all possible industrial product-objects,
 - to plan and create single, full-automatic machines,
- to control the performance of these machines and product-chains,
 - to use Computers (in companies and private) correctly,
- generally, the Human Being is the single living, intelligent kernel and head of our Digital Society. Human Being can't be resituated in our Digital Society.

Look at Authors Homepage: <http://www.plbg.at> in German and English. He has written down a Paradigm for Orientation of IT towards Human Being (<http://www.plbg.at/humanorientierung.aspx>) (German and English) in 2016. It can be read and downloaded as Open Source.

The kernel is:

- ✚ Mentally not high levelled, individual, manual agitations stay enduring necessary too.
- ✚ We know that actually in average western Industrial Countries 60% of working places are situated in Small and Medium Companies.

- ✚ Rest is working in agriculture, services and in industrial great companies with 100, 500, 1000 up to and over 5000 employed persons.
- ✚ Learned, manual professions are still necessary and searched. They are in Digital Age actually not published „fascinating“ enough.
- ✚ Inside of single companies „Rich“ as well as „Poor“ are working. They fit together like their single, different challenges according to their different single abilities.
- ✚ Every good steered company can be an individual direct internal social upgrade from Poor to Rich.

4.4. How much are poor, how much rich?

In our Digital Society in latest publications by NGO's is said that **it's possible worldwide to delete permanent poorness**. That's a real new fact for first time of Humanity.

It makes sense for first time in history of whole Humanity to follow on this way and try to make it real – in a worldwide common way. The biological and physical facts of necessary resources are existing; we only have to organise it worldwide in a motivating way.

In our western Industrial Society about 10 – 20 % are poor. In Austria the level of poorness is around 10-12% of population. But that's not typical worldwide, of course.

The defined social state between Poor and Rich is dependent on ownership, income, salary for employed work and the Social Insurances (Loss of Work, Illness and Pension).

Employers can be levelled, in Information scientific way, as rich. Rich can be defined as: financially, existentially having more than ought to live sustainably, healthy and cultured.

Poor can be said for that people which have no permanent ownership or salary for living so as they need. These people are registered in western, European, social States by established social organisations. They get a legislative-fixed „Minimum Salary“.

These organisations are deciding criteria's for being allowed to carry the attribute „Social State“ or not. To these social areas of a state belong mainly Unemployment-, Health- and Pension-Insurance Systems. That this isn't usual worldwide, got known recently by leading western Industrial Country USA. A talented president in latest times (Barack OBAMA, 2008-2016) showed the reality, that USA is till now no common Social State. They have no functioning common social system and his successor as president even wanted to delete these activities.

As special social groups in every state the author will signify:

- ✚ State Official's, Politicians,
- ✚ voluntary members, without and with salary, members of Church Organisations.

State Official's and timely bordered Politicians get normally a good positioned stately salary and social background.

Church Organisations are the single, genuine highlights for functioning social structures. But they base on religious princip's, which are brought voluntarily (religiose way of living, partly or full celibacy and partly personal poorness). Look in Reference List: Laszlo ZSOLNAI, Franciscan Spirituality and Economics (2018).

The way to a genuine, enduring Social State is stony and worldwide in main parts restricted to rich Industrial Countries. Even there (see USA) it's not installed over all social groups.

4.5. Found, global scientific entries

A welcomed, first, system analytical entry was made in 1972 at MIT, USA.

Prof. Jay W. FORRESTER created a „World Model“ as base, called „System Dynamics“. The original result can be found around pp. 88-91 in **Dennis MEADOWS, The Limits to Growth**, in Reference List.

Jorgen RANDERS, who was already included in this first report of MIT 1972 to the Club of Rome, has written in 1912 a further paper. It's findable in the Reference List too. He dared even a forecast till 2052, what's nearly impossible for a dying Human. But he has made real warnings and hints for future dangers – usable for scientific building of opinions.

Seen out of Information Science these designs are usual business. So, the author can extract the main terms of Jay W. FORRESTER, Dennis MEADOWS und Jorgen RANDERS and add own ones:

- + raw materials: not renewable, rate of their consumption, actually very much searched Rare Earths,
 - + dividing of genuine used land for living, industry and agriculture,
 - + population, rate of birth and dye, global and regional,
 - + fertility, food, per head,
 - + consume, per head,
 - + working places in agriculture, in services and in industry,
 - + common services are a very new, not yet satisfying balanced source of working places,
 - + Industry Output (products and capital),
 - + generation of energy, new forms of energy,
 - + protection of environment, sustainability of landscape conservation,
 - + regional and global pollution of environment,
 - + global errors and ought corrections, possible rates of success and time intervals.

All these terms can be brought into a complex relation system. But it's not seriously possible to guaranty definitive results. We only can recognise relations and influences, they are no definitive nature laws. Jorgen RANDERS (see Reference List) writes in his work that previews of artificially created systems only can take care on in present time registered data. In future they only can be a possible forecast under supposed conditions. In Computer Science these systems are called „Simulations“ and are possible easily.

But actual fears in connection with Climate Catastrophes are quite serious. We can hope only that the global intentions to reduce the causes will succeed. That's a goal for Good Will backed by necessary understanding. Information Science can do a lot for it.

The personal impulse of the author is to create an artificial, chemical environment which can f. i. fractionise CO², CH₄, N₂O or latest in China refund CFC-11 in the air into their atomic elements. So, we have to correct our errors in connection to nature.

The actually globally most propogates reduction of burning of C is of course

the most efficient way. But the global industry isn't yet willing to follow this goal consequently. We have to inform more and more and have to motivate to bring the deciding political powers to do something.

This isn't possible enough till now, so we have to give it to the next generation of Humans. They have to live in the possible bad conditions in their future. They have energy enough to do something.

6. Poorness as term

That term exactly has been differentiated from his profane character in European Culture by Catholic Mendicant Orders (founded by Francisco of Assisi or Dominicus Savio). Generally, by Francisco of Assisi the term **Poorness** was separated from the term **Poverty**. He said: "poorness makes happy – but in case of poverty has to be helped". Look in Reference List **Thomas und Gertrude SARTORY, Franz von Assisi Geliebte Armut, 1991, p. 14.**

Besides the materialistic circumstances of ownership are mental states of mind important. For happiness of a Human Being isn't his possession deciding but his satisfaction about that he needs really.

"To Have or To Be" have got characteristic keywords of the young generation at about 1970. Look at Reference List **Erich FROMM**. The youth at that time was just born in the time after World War II.

In an existentially endangered poverty (not enough for eating, no cloths, no living room, no health assurance) own laws are valid. Every healthy society and every democratic state have to fight against that permanently.

We have to see the terms „churchy poverty“ and „stately poorness“ as equal in meaning. The „churchy poorness“ is in genuine “stately value scales” not possible and has to be seen separated.

In these circumstances are actions necessary – inside all states worldwide.

7. Richness, seen absolutely

Richness even in Bible is signed out as a possible danger for healthy, Human feeling. It's not really generally damned. It endangers when it gets an enforcement without joy and mentally satisfying content. The Human Being is then by "his challenges to be rich" fully obtained (meanness) and has lost interest in mental freedom and feelings or culture. He/she also can lose the live contact to his Human surrounding by (not founded) fear of existence. A rich Human Being is permanently exposed to pressure by social envy. That can make a single person to a loner or crack in his social surroundings. So, he/she has to take care – more than the not rich ones – on being positive thinking, generous (but not luxuriant), helpful and integrated in his Human society.

Richness is a life goal of every poor man because he combines richness with happiness absolutely. Only when a poor man has got rich, he realises the great backsides. Richness is of course generally a desirable goal – but we have to take care on "no hurting of Human neighbours". Always being helping and friendly is best way of life and makes happy surely.

Let us fix: not richness but social balance and satisfaction is the most precious economic goal.

8. Conclusio, found Results

- ✚ Social **balance** it not social equalising,
- ✚ individual goals and actions of will of **single persons** are allowed, even are **precious** in economy,
- ✚ **communities of interest** make the success of social balanced goals easier to reach,
- ✚ **Acts of Nature beyond Control** can be prevented and organised positively in a Catastrophically Management,
- ✚ **poverty** can and has to be fought commonly worldwide,
- ✚ conscious, by Human Being planned and founded **changes by force** should be prohibited by all Human abilities,
- ✚ modern **communication** between civilised, good educated and cultivated Human brings **peaceful, social changes** in most cases,
- ✚ **direct, interhuman dialog** is and stays the most precious exchange of Information,
- ✚ **a wise and cultivated Human Being** is and stays the kernel and head in our Digital Age, he/she is not resettable.

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